

**Special Issue
“EHMA 2023 Abstract Book”**

Guest Editors: Prof. Sandra C. Buttigieg, MD; Prof. Americo Cicchetti; Prof Axel Kaehne; Dr Alexandre Lourenço; Dr Teppo Heikkilä, MD, EMBA; Prof Todorka Kostadinova; Dr Eszter Kovacs; Prof Federico Lega; Prof Ann Mahon; Dr Rui Dang; Nabil Jamshed MSc MBA BBA; Prof Dr Marija Jevtic, MD; Prof Dr Teresa Magalhães; Prof Dr Henk Nies; Prof Mag Dr Manfred Pferzinger; Prof Dr Rui Santana; Dr Federica Morandi; Mr George Valiotis

[Introduction to the Special Issue](#)

Prof. Sandra C. Buttigieg, Prof. Americo Cicchetti

Abstracts in the Special issue

[Experiencing and witnessing disruptive behaviours towards nurses in COVID-19 teams, patient safety and errors in care](#)

Dr Gillie Gabay, Dr Sigal Shfran-Tikva, Prof Avi Kluger, Ms Liron Asraf

[Towards sustainable health workforces: the roles of governance, planning and data](#)

Dr Gareth H Rees, Mr Cris Scotter, Dr Rosemary James, Mr Levan Samadashvili

[Workplace ostracism undermines work well-being in healthcare](#)

Ms Sirpa M. Manninen, Prof Sanna Laulainen, Prof Timo Sinervo, Mr Samuli Koponen

[Utilising dormant workforce talent: developing, supporting & integrating multinational doctors in England through the medical support worker \(MSW\) programme, a sustainable workforce initiative](#)

Dr William Sacre, Dr Rachel Rajadurai, Mr Thomas Kearney, Dr Ivan Trotman, Mr Manraj Dighal, Dr Celia Ingham Clark

[A realist review of the international literature demonstrating how governance and decision-making during the 2008 financial crisis impacted health workforce resilience for COVID-19 and future health system shocks](#)

Dr Padraic Fleming, Dr Louise Caffrey, Dr Sara VanBelle, Dr Sarah Barry, Dr Sara Burke, Ms Jacki Conway, Dr Rikke Siersbaek, Mr David Mockler, Prof Steve Thomas

[The role of governance modes in dealing with complexity of healthcare systems: evidence from three regions in Italy](#)

Dr Natalia Oprea, MSc Gianmario Cinelli, MSc Michela Bobini, Prof Francesco Longo, Prof Mario Del Vecchio

About the EHMA Conference

The EHMA Conference is Europe's preeminent conference on health management. Each year it gathers the full healthcare ecosystem, including health managers and leaders, healthcare professionals, researchers, academics, industry representatives, and decision-makers from Europe, and beyond.

The EHMA Conference provides a platform to discuss the latest health management research, tools and evidence from renowned researchers, academics and professionals. It is concerned on translating research into practice. It creates opportunities for dialogue and exchange on solutions to ensure the sustainability and resilience of health systems.

The EHMA 2023 Annual Conference

EHMA 2023 is the 28th edition of our Annual Conference.

This year's conference theme is 'Health management: sustainable solutions for complex systems'. Three years of the COVID pandemic have exposed gaps and vulnerabilities in European health systems, and the immense pressure on the health and care workforce. Sustainable solutions and strategic thinking are needed to drive the transformation of health systems.

EHMA 2023 is structured around five tracks that reflect the holistic practice of health management, and frame the lenses through which contemporary topics are analysed and discussed.

The European Health Management Association

The European Health Management Association (EHMA) strives for excellent health management for a healthy Europe by supporting the spread of knowledge on effective health management practices. Active since 1982, EHMA exists so that Europe's citizens and communities can benefit from quality, safe, value-based care and health systems.

Our focus is on enhancing the capacity and capabilities of health management to deliver high-quality healthcare and support the successful implementation of health policy. Our commitment is on supporting the provision of data and research findings for evidence-based decision-making and monitoring health policies and practices.

EHMA is the only membership organisation in Europe to bring together the full health management ecosystem, including health and hospital managers, healthcare professionals, researchers, academia, policy and decision-makers. We are a recognised and respected amplifier of best practices in the evolution of health management, and we provide an environment where evidence, challenge and experience are valued and complex debates on current topics can take place.

Development of a model of digital healthcare ecosystem based on blockchain technology

Dr Daniel Bjelica¹, Prof Dr Aleksandra Labus¹, Prof Dr Marija Jevtic^{2,3}, Prof Dr Artur Bjelica²

¹*Faculty of Organisational Sciences, Serbia.* ²*Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia.*

³*Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB), Research centre on Environmental and Occupational Health, School of Public Health, Belgium*

Blockchain technology represents an innovative approach to remodeling the healthcare system that offers a wide range of integrated functions: data access flexibility, security, privacy, decentralised storage, transparency, immutability, authentication, disintermediation, verifiability, programmability, and interconnection. As an initial step in the project of planning the application of blockchain technology in the digital health ecosystem, it is necessary to determine the key stakeholders who will be involved in the implementation. For the blockchain-based projects, nodes represent the basis of the blockchain network. Typical nodes in the handling of electronic health information are doctors and other medical personnel, pharmacists, healthcare facilities, laboratories. Each of the mentioned entities or nodes has a requirement that the data is safe, reliable and efficiently processed within the unified complete medical history. In addition, when planning the application of blockchain technology in the digital health ecosystem, the readiness of stakeholders for the thorough implementation of blockchain-based projects should also be taken into consideration. Experience on stakeholder readiness for blockchain implementation can be drawn from the research on blockchain implementation in other sectors.

We propose a model of a digital health ecosystem based on blockchain technology with the following characteristics:

The core model is represented by two databases – patient health records and data of business transactions carried out by the health institution with other stakeholders in the digital health ecosystem.

The model supports two levels of data interoperability: patient-centric and institutional interoperability.

In relation to patients, the formulation of the model is patient-centric, thus promoting a qualitatively new level of data interoperability.

Institutional data interoperability is supported in the proposed model through the exchange of information of the health care institution with other stakeholders.

Key data transactions in the proposed model are based on the application of blockchain technology.

The application of blockchain technology in the given model enables the management and verification of data without intermediaries, without compromising authenticity, with continuous availability, verifiability of data and the existence of complete transparency.

Based on preliminary investigation, the developed model is planned to be implemented in a private healthcare organisation in the Republic of Serbia.